

TYPES OF LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY SHOWING WHICH GENDER IN THE SPEECH OF LANGUAGE OWNERS.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hozirgi zamonaviy tilshunoslik yo'nalinishlaridan biri bo'lgan lingvopersonologiyaning o'rganish obyekti va lisoniy shaxs tiplari, lisoniy shaxs nutqida uchraydigan nutqiy jarayonga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar haqida, shuningdek, nutq egalaringning shaxsiy sifatlariga ko'ra lisoniy shaxs tiplaridan biri bo'lgan qaysi jinsga mansubligini namoyon etuvchi lisoniy shaxs tiplari xususida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Lisoniy shaxs, til, nutq, shaxsiy sifatlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье объектом изучения лингвоперсонологии, которая является одним из направлений современного языкознания, и типов языковой личности, влияние на речевой процесс в речи языковой личности речь идет об указывающих факторах, а также о типах языковой личности, показывающих, к какому полу они принадлежат, что является одним из типов языковой личности по личностным качествам говорящих.

Ключевые слова: Языковая личность, язык, речь, личностные качества

Abstract: In this article, the object of study of linguopersonology, which is one of the directions of modern linguistics, and the types of linguistic person, the influence on the speech process in the speech of a linguistic person

it is discussed about the indicating factors, as well as about the types of linguistic personality that show which gender they belong to, which is one of the types of linguistic personality according to the personal qualities of the speakers.

Key words: Linguistic personality, language, speech, personal qualities.

In this case, linguistic personality types are distinguished based on the gender of the speakers. According to this characteristic, the following types of linguistic personality can be distinguished: linguistic personality type specific to women's speech, linguistic personality type specific to men's speech. Also, linguistic personality types are distinguished based on the gender and age of the person can be distinguished: a linguistic personality type specific to the speech of old women, a linguistic personality type specific to the speech of old men, a linguistic personality type specific to the speech of girls, and a linguistic personality type specific to the speech of young men.

The gender specificity of speech is determined by certain signs. ZR Khachmafova notes that in prose works, the female linguistic personality is determined at the verbal-semantic level of the language, in cognitive phenomena represented by concepts, ideas, stereotypes that take place in the gender picture of the world, reflecting the hierarchy of values; in the pragmatic framework that includes goals, motives, interests, instructions and intentions. She singled out the following cases of the manifestation of the female linguistic personality based on materials from the Russian and German languages:

1) the focus of the message is on women, the female subject (the message is expressed in first-person language, "female autobiography");

2) depiction of the everyday life of ordinary people, especially women (family, home, children, parents, spouse, friends, the "love trinity", betrayal, jealousy, etc.);

3) in the structure of a feminine text, family and kinship relationships are more important than other types of social relationships;

4) addressing the topic of domestic violence (wife-husband) and occupational discrimination (worker-boss);

5) the issue of relationships with the opposite sex comes to the fore as one of the reasons for the existentialization of femininity in understanding one's own "I";

6) in literature, the experience of women is often expressed in terms of physical, biological, physiological, etc., in contrast to the literary tradition of men;

7) the intertwining of different discourse levels (discourses) and a series of leitmotifs.

The aspects noted by the scientist are mainly extralinguistic factors, and certain linguistic means used in speech can also create gender stereotypes.

Based on the analysis of Uzbek language materials, it is possible to distinguish linguistic means that reflect the gender specificity of speech, as well as extralinguistic means that accompany them in speech:

1) units of address specific to male and female speech;

2) emotionally charged words, phrases, and occasional connotative expressions typical of male and female speech;

3) units of the non-literary layer used in male and female speech (units expressing insults, curses, humiliation, petting, etc., nicknames);

4) units expressing different evaluative attitudes in male and female speech;

5) tone, pause, and tempo of pronunciation characteristic of male and female speech;

6) nonverbal means used in male and female speech (behavior, facial expressions), etc.

These signs serve to clarify whether the speech belongs to a man or a woman. Let's analyze the following text:

– *He cursed at me like that yesterday, he cursed at me like that, you young man, just die! ...*

– *He cursed at my mother, you're rotting in your grave.*

"Don't be sad," my mother tried to comfort her.

– *Why shouldn't I be upset? ... – I crushed the tumor in the evening. I put it on my eyebrow so that it wouldn't dry out. Yes, I took the mosquito net under my chin and it hardened. Is that why my father is a judge? "If you look at your food instead of your makeup, you'll die!" he says, you idiot! Yes, if I put on makeup, I'll play, you'll be angry with your barber! Is it a joke, a joke, don't you eat your poison, just swallow it! Hah, your tongue that cursed my mother will stick to your palate! What else will you say? He blames me: your tongue is a span, he says.*

"Oh, my tongue, let it be a piece of cake when you speak my language. If it comes like the wind and goes like the flood, I will never agree!"

"Stop it, you fool," my mother smiled sadly. "There is a house without food, there is no house without war... Don't curse the poor thing."

– *Oh, why don't you curse me? Blood is coming out of your mouth and nose in clots, why don't you curse me? I'm leaving! (O'.Hoshimov. "The Affairs of the World")*

This text depicts a conversation between two women. These women appear in the text as female interlocutors. The fact that one of the interlocutors is a woman is understood through the use of the pronoun *ovsinjon* in her speech.

The individual lexicon of the speakers served to indicate the gender nature of their speech. The curses used in the speech (you may die, you may be cut by the sword, you may eat the earth, you may stick to your tongue, you may have a lump of meat in your tongue, you may have clots of blood from your mouth and nose), units expressing evaluative attitudes (like, like), connotative expressions formed on the basis of repetition (such a curse, such a curse, such a curse), and uses specific to women's speech (I crushed a tumor, I put it on my eyebrows, if I make up, oh, why don't I curse) demonstrated the gender nature of the speech. The intonational characteristics of speech (rhetorical question, exclamatory intonation, etc.) and events reflected in the text, such as putting on a wig, putting on makeup, and putting on a mask, also provide information about the gender nature of the speech.

Thus, according to the manifestation of the gender sign, linguistic personality types differ based on the gender of the speakers. According to this sign, the following types of linguistic personality can be distinguished: linguistic personality type specific to women's speech, linguistic personality type specific to men's speech.

Literature:

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